

Ayushman Bharat: An Interplay of the Rights-based approach and Welfarism

Rajshree*

Department of Political Science, Jesus and Mary College, University of Delhi, New Delhi 11001, India

E-mail: rajshree122000@gmail.com

Abstract. The study aims to analyse the Ayushman Bharat Scheme as interplay of the rights-based approach and welfarism, determine the feasibility of Universal Health Coverage, ascertain the effects of ‘profit-sector’ inclusion and understand its role-play in the pandemic of COVID-19. The Ayushman Bharat-National Health Protection Scheme has been viewed by many as a populist scheme favoring the private sector. It has been exemplified as the world’s largest scheme with financial protection of coverage up to five lakh per family per year with its focus on the ‘vulnerable and deprived population’ based on the Socio-economic Caste Census. The scheme seeks to achieve universal health coverage through a partnership between the public and the private sector and cooperative federalism, claiming to overcome the loopholes of the subsumed Rashtriya Suraksha Bima Yojana. A review of literature is adopted as a research methodology to ascertain and analyse the Ayushman Bharat Scheme in the paradigm of the rights-based approach. The review will specifically search, identify, analyse and synthesize the different areas of the scheme. Descriptive and Inferential Statistics based on secondary research has been used to validate the analysis thus drawn from the findings. Based on the findings, it can be stated that Ayushman Bharat National Health Protection Scheme is a policy fulfilling Article 21 and Directive Principle of State Policy Article 41, providing financial protection to ‘vulnerable and deprived population.’ Universal Health Coverage will face a great deal of challenge given the shortfall of rural infrastructure and specialist doctors and will thus increase the burden on urban healthcare institutions. Though public-private partnership has been developed to assist and achieve the goal of universal health coverage, the ‘profit-sector’ has been accused of corruption, unnecessary and costlier services. As an effect of COVID-19, there have been lower claims of AB-PMJAY in public healthcare institutions, while the footfall has increased in the private hospitals, mainly because many government hospitals have been converted to ‘COVID hospitals’, due to fear of transmission and the quality and wide range of treatments provided by the private health sector.

Keywords: Ayushman Bharat, National Health Policy, Privatization, Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana

Introduction

The preamble of the Indian Constitution defines India to be, ‘Sovereign, Socialist, Secular, Democratic, Republic.’ The term socialist calls attention to the need or demand for the state to make appropriate, timely intervention to fulfil the ‘positive’ rights of the citizens and to establish social justice and welfarism. There are ample welfare policies launched by the Indian government historically from Pradhan Mantri Grameen Awaas Yojana to Atal Pension Yojana to the recent Ayushman Bharat Scheme. Some policies are launched voluntarily while some are launched as an effect of the vigilant judgements of the judiciary based on the interpretation of the Constitution.

Though these policies may be advertised by the government as a privilege or an extraordinary task been fulfilled, it is important to take into account how many of these policies are basic necessities and are a citizen's very basic right to claim. Universal Declaration of Human Rights defines a rights-based approach as a justifiable entitlement, with human dignity and worth, to basic services like food, education, health, employment (Pawar, 2012). In India, many of the welfare policies are based on the rights-based approach. The root of the rights-based approach in India comes from the Article 21, the ‘Right to life’ of the constitution which states, “No person shall be deprived of his life or personal

liberty except according to the procedure established by law.” The approach is validated by the non-enforceable claims of Directive principles of the state policy, of which Article 41 states, “within the limits of its economic capacity and development, make effective provision for securing the right to work, to education, to public assistance, in cases of unemployment, old age, sickness and disablement and other cases of undeserved want” (Srivastava, 2008 Pg 112).

One of the similar pro-poor welfare policies launched by the Government of India in 2018 is the Ayushman Bharat Scheme. The scheme promises to provide health insurance that will cover about 100 million poor families and providing 0.5 million per family per year, thus making it the world’s largest government-aided insurance scheme (Gopichandran & Subramaniam, 2019). As per the Lancet Journal, India is ranked 154 out of 195 countries in health service delivery index (Lahariya, 2020). Not only this, but 22% of the Indian population is below the poverty line as of 2011-12 as per the data revealed by the planning commission of India in 2013. This indicates the dire need of transforming healthcare policy.

The Ayushman Bharat Scheme consists of two components. First, the establishment of the Health and Wellness Centre and second, the National Health Protection Scheme (Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana) (Hooda, 2020). The Health and Wellness Centres (HWCs) are supposed to be formed with up-gradation of the already existing primary healthcare centres, urban primary healthcare centres and the sub-health centres. On the other hand, the Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana is an insurance scheme to allow access to the public as well as private health institutions with coverage of five lakh per annum 10.74 poor families. The major aim of the policy is to provide financial protection to a certain section of the population i.e. reduce out of pocket expenditure and increase access to quality health and expenditure, thus improving the population health outcomes (Divyesh, n.d.).

The research article will try to analyse the preparedness of the existing healthcare institutions to provide universal health coverage. It will try to analyse the effects of private sector involvement in the scheme and challenges that the scheme is going to face in the implementation process. It will also try to find out its role-play in the on-going pandemic of COVID-19.

Major Features of the Ayushman Bharat scheme

Ayushman Bharat is a national-level program announced in the year 2018 by the Central government. Health is one of the basic building factors of the capability of an individual which allows him to achieve fulfilment in his life. Health has always been neglected as an issue, thus the announcement of such world’s largest healthcare scheme has been seen with a lot of hope and expectation.

There are two major components of the program. First, the formation of the 1,50,000 Health and Wellness Centre by the year 2022 and second, the National Health Protection Scheme later renamed as Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (PMJAY) which aims to provide financial protection for secondary and tertiary level hospitalization. Under the policy, the public can avail services in both public and registered private hospitals.

The first task of the program is to establish the Health and Wellness Centers (HWCs) by upgrading the existing 1, 50,000 sub-health centers and primary health centers. HWCs seeks to broaden the services old-age care, oral, nose, eye, throat, lung disease, hypertension, common cancers, mental and adolescent health, and other free essential diagnostic services. The basic idea is to allow the accessibility of the services within thirty minutes of distance by civil society. The plan is set to be achieved in a step by step manner. The target of 15,000 centers in the first year of 2018-2019, 40,000 in the year of 2019-2020, and 70,000 in the year 2020-2021.

The second task is the establishment of the government-funded healthcare insurance scheme called the Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (PMJAY) which aims to provide a coverage of up to Rs. 5, 00,000 per family per year covering both secondary and tertiary level hospitalization services. The scheme is set to colligate the existing policies of Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojana and Senior Citizen Health insurance scheme.

Figure 1. Budget estimates and budget allocation 2014-2019 in the Health sector (in crores)

Source: PRS

The standalone factor of the policy is its focus on the ‘vulnerable and deprived population’ based on the Socio-economic Caste Census, thus going beyond the conventional ‘below poverty line’ paradigm.

In the union budget 2020, the budget allocation for the health sector stands at 1.15% of the gross domestic product which has been promised to be doubled by 2025. The total of Rs 69,000 crore is said to be assigned for the health sector of which Rs 6,400 crores will be granted for AB-PMJAY. **Figure 1** portrays the budget estimates and actual expenditure (in crores) from the year 2014 to 2019.

To fulfil the laid out plans, the government will set up four bodies. First, National Health Protection Council will be set up to provide policy guidance to AB-NHPM, co-chaired by Union Health and Family Welfare Minister and Vice-Chairman of National Institute of Transforming India. Second, Ayushman Bharat National Health Protection Mission Governing body whose function will be to make decisions. Third, Ayushman Bharat- National Health Protection Mission Agency to manage AB-NHPM at the operational level in the form of society. Fourth, the State Health Agency will be established in every state of India to implement the scheme. The implementation will take place through an insurance company or a trust. **Figure 2** portrays the institutional structure of the scheme.

Figure 2. Institutional Structure of the scheme

The Feasibility of Universal Health Coverage

The universal health coverage is expected to be achieved through a partnership with private providers along with the functioning of the public health system. This has to be achieved through financial protection provided by the government-aided finance health insurance under Ayushman Bharat-National Health Protection Mission (AB-NHPM). The policy aims to, "...achieve universal health coverage including financial risk protection, access to quality essential healthcare services, access to safe, effective, quality and affordable essential medicines and vaccines for all."

The success of the program will be dependent on the ability of the targeted population (10 crores) to avail the promised services i.e. hospitalization and comprehensive primary healthcare services.

AB-NHPM will require an estimate budget allocation of INR 200 billion on reaching its full coverage which is significantly much higher than the actual budget allotment, which in the year 2018 was INR 20 billion only (Gopichandran & Subramaniam, 2019). Given the precedent, it's questionable for the government to cover the set targets.

The program is based on the idea of cooperative federalism where the central government is expected to make sixty per cent of the expenditure while the state government is expected to make forty per cent which will come about 4000 crores as per Niti Aayog estimates. With many of the states running their healthcare welfare programs, it has been questioned whether the states will be ready to a larger amount of the scheme.

Another important challenge in the achievement of UHC is the unavailability and shortfall of rural infrastructure and specialist doctors which in turn forces the rural population to avail for services in the urban areas. Thus, increasing the burden of patients on urban health infrastructure. Not only this the scheme is focused on secondary and tertiary services which are provided mainly in the urban areas.

By May 15th, 2019, twenty lakh claims have been preauthorized with an average of Rs 13,000. Of the total cases, 7% are high value claims (above 30,000 INR) while, 1% are very high-value claims (above INR 1 lakh) (Dong&Naib, 2020). Analyzing the high-value claims inter-state, the highest of the availment has been done in Maharashtra, Dadra and Nagar Haveli, Daman and Diu, Karnataka, Chhattisgarh and Tamil Nadu. The beneficiaries of these high-claims have mostly been men which indicates the gendered-access to specialized and costly treatments like cardio-surgery packages.

The AB-National Health Protection Scheme is often termed as an upgraded Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojana (RSBY) with the major aim to tackle the increasing out of the pocket expenditure which has pushed more and more rural population below the poverty line (Malhi et. al, 2020). The RSBY has set a precedent and thus helps in overcoming the loopholes and implementation hassles faced before and which are needed to be excelled. RSBY's goal was to allow greater access to quality healthcare services including hospitalization and surgery facilities to the below poverty line families. It had an annual coverage of Rs. 30,000 per household engulfing hospitalization, consultations, medicines, daycare treatment.

AB-NHPS is an improvement over RSBY. The new policy is entitlement based while the earlier policy was enrolment-based. Thus, the identified population will get covered automatically, once the scheme starts functioning. The scheme is fully funded by the Central and the state government. Therefore, there is no risk or resource pooling. There is also a significant increase in the coverage cop for a single household, i.e. five lakh per family.

History has shown how the insurance coverage is insufficient i.e. though the coverage has remained the same the hospital costs have only increased. What has also been pointed out the lack of rural infrastructure and the involvement of the private sector in unethical methods of extracting money like in the case of conducting unnecessary surgeries.

Therefore, though the motive of the scheme has been to achieve welfarism, and lead to the fulfilment of rights of citizen certain loopholes in the policy like the rural infrastructure, insufficient budget allotment keeps it from achieving its goals.

Effects of Private Sector Inclusion

An important aspect of the scheme is the inclusion of the private sector and the endorsement of public-private-partnership (PPP) in the implementation process and the achievement of the goals. The motive of the Health and Wellness Centers (HWCs) is to upgrade the primary healthcare centers into comprehensive primary healthcare centers to provide secondary and tertiary hospitalization services.

To achieve this, Niti Aayog came up with the model of PPP in the year 2017, even before the implementation of the Ayushman Bharat Scheme. The essential factor to establish PPP is to have a fair amount of patient load at the district hospitals preferably, a thousand outpatient department per day (Hooda, 2020).

It sets to create a downward linkage with the existing Primary Health Centers (PHCs) and Community Health Centers (CHCs) of the districts and the neighborhood district. This will later help in identifying centers which are to be converted to the Health and Wellness Centers (HWCs) with special significance on non-communicable diseases care detection. So, the goal is to launch the HWCs as a reference to allow upward mobility in the facility chain, and thus enhance the implementation of the PPPs.

The government has set up special provisions to stimulate the private sector:

- 1) A special window for clearances within a specific time.
- 2) Timely payment of the services provided through the Chief Minister Wellness funds or PMJAY.
- 3) A fair amount of patient load at the district hospitals ascertained by establishing downward linkages with Community Health Centers and Primary Health Centers.
- 4) Improving the financial viability and bankability of the project through viability gap funding (VGF).

The scheme is based on efficient engagement with the 'for profit' providers (Gopichandran & Subramaniam, 2019). There lies an asymmetry between the knowledge present between the suppliers and the receivers. Such a gap leads to suppliers deciding what has to be provided and how much is to be provided. This allows the profit-seeking institutions to provide costlier and unnecessary services to extract money out of patients. Other than this, the involvement of the private sector is voluntary. Therefore, they may step-back anytime leaving the scheme without a partner and back-up to rely upon. In India, every 10,000 patients have access to only nine hospital beds and six doctors. The implementation of the scheme will lead to a great deal of burden not only on public sectors healthcare institutions but also that of the private. The lack of hospital beds in India is best exemplified by the recent pandemic of COVID-19 which has been an eye-opener. There is also a disproportionate allocation of the healthcare budget. While twenty-five per cent of the budget is said to be allocated to the National Health Protection Scheme, the rest of the seventy-five per cent will go in feeding the private sector.

Ayushman Bharat and COVID-19

The pandemic of COVID-19 has been an eye-opener for the Indian healthcare system. The numbers of affected people have only been increasing despite continuous lockdowns induced by the central and state governments. The pandemic has also affected the capability of the hospitals in the provision of the healthcare services and the willingness of the citizens to avail these services. **Figure 3** describes the effects of Coronavirus on both healthcare institutions and the citizens.

Figure 3. Effects of COVID-19 on the Supplier and Demand-side

Source: Smith, et.al, 2020

The key comeback of the Indian government in fighting the coronavirus has been the establishment of make-shift isolation wards in the existing healthcare institutions and the reallocation of the resources for setting up of the quarantine and isolation services. There are two significant policy formulations which are dubious in the time of the pandemic (Gopichandran & Subramaniam, 2019). First, a greater focus on private healthcare sector leading to the weakening of the public healthcare institutions. Second, giving greater significance to hospital-based treatments than upon public health and preventive treatments.

To control the spread of the outbreak, information through a robust surveillance system is seen to be an important mechanism to track all the patients that may be affected by the virus. The greatest number of affected people, as well as fatality, has been reported in the countries with the world's best healthcare systems. On the other hand, the tracking is easier in authoritative countries and well-developed countries like China and Scandinavian countries, respectively. India, unfortunately, has not been a winner on the side of tracking affected people, which is an important reason for the increase of cases. Along with this, enhanced laboratory services are to be built for conducting as many tests as possible.

It was in early April 2020 that the government made the testing and treatment of COVID-19 eligible under AB-PMJAY in reduced costs in private hospitals and free in the public healthcare centers. National Health Authority (NHA), the body responsible for the implementation of the AB-PMJAY, announced in the month of May 2020 about 2,300 patients availing free COVID-19 treatments in hospitals under Ayushman Bharat and about 3,000 patients being tested for the infection (PTI, 2020). They have made an exemplary usage of Information Technology to connect with patients, answer their queries and work on the ground level. A call-center has been established as a COVID-19 helpline center with over 700 employees dealing with the queries of citizens along with starting 'Ask Ayushman' chat box on WhatsApp. Applications have been developed which will allow the citizen to

rank the hospitals based on their services through, 'Hospital Ranking Dashboard'. State governments have launched their local applications for social auditing. The central government-aided application, 'Aarogya Setu' plays a prominent role with regular assessment of citizens and calls given to those who have COVID-19 like symptoms and later connecting them with doctors.

The research conducted by the National Health Authority (NHA) revealed the sudden decline of patients availing facilities in public hospitals. Private hospitals are being preferred over the public as citizens fear transmission. This has mainly been due to, First, the conversion of many public hospitals into "COVID 19 facilities." Second, the government hospitals would have been too involved in the preparation of hospitals for the pandemic. There has also been a decline in the volume of the availment in the claims under PM-JAY by sixty-four per cent in the early lockdown phase (Smith, et.al., 2020) While the lockdown value declined by seventy-six per cent.

In terms of inter-state variations, the steepest declines have been observed in the states of Assam (97%), Maharashtra (80%) and Bihar (76%) while the smallest decline in the states of Uttrakhand (16%), Punjab (17%) and Kerala (26%) as shown in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4. Inter-state variation in the decline of the utilisation of PM-JAY

Source: Smith, et.al, 2020

Recommendations to overcome the challenges in the Implementation

A well-implemented policy is a well worked out policy. The Ayushman Bharat Scheme is said to be a people's policy based on the idea of welfarism, an improvement over the Rashtriya Suraksha Bima Yojana. To overcome the challenges and better implementation following recommendations are made:

1. To allow better functioning of the Health and Wellness Centre (HWC), it is important to make the healthcare institutions at the ground level accountable. Therefore, an enhanced authority shall be granted to the states, which then be made responsible for the proper functioning of all the district and sub-district rural and urban centers.
2. Another important step to make healthcare institutions accountable and policy successful is to have regular interactions and engagements with the stakeholders. The stakeholders involved in the assessment of the functioning of the policy at the ground level make excellent judgements which in turn could help in the improvement of the policy and rectify any mistakes made.
3. A separate body shall be formed to assess the workings of the private sector under the scheme. It should be ensured that the 'profit-sector' doesn't involve in any foul-play. An application should be developed to rate the hospitals based on the quality of the treatment provided. This will lead to a stronger citizen-government relationship.
4. The policy will not able to achieve its goals until an improvement in the healthcare infrastructure is made, particularly the rural infrastructure. The pandemic of COVID-19 has revealed the dark secrets of the medical sector of India. What is the use of the policy when the infrastructure is nit promising? Thus, its high time that the government starts emphasizing on tangible improvements.

Conclusion

India ranks 145th out of 195 countries in terms of accessibility to healthcare in the Lancet study. Health is an important aspect to allow the individual to develop to her fullest potential. The Right to life is an umbrella claim, which within itself also contain the Right to Health. The Ayushman Bharat Scheme claims itself to be the world's largest health insurance scheme proving a coverage of INR five lakh per to five lakh per family per year with its focus on the 'vulnerable and deprived population'. There are two pillars of the policy, first, the establishment of the Health and Wellness Centres and second, the National Health Protection Scheme later renamed as Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (PMJAY). To fulfil the plans four bodies are supposed to be established namely, First, National Health Protection Mission, Second, Ayushman Bharat National Health Protection Mission Governing body, Third, Ayushman Bharat- National Health Protection Mission Agency and Fourth, the State Health Agency. Universal Healthcare Coverage is challenging to be achieved given the insufficient insurance coverage and shortfall of rural infrastructure. The private sector involvement in the scheme is voluntary, which means a step-back by the 'profit-hospital' may leave the system high and dry. The pandemic of COVID-19 has led the healthcare sector to the establishment of make-shift isolation wards in the existing healthcare institutions and the reallocation of the resources for setting up of the quarantine and isolation services. What has also been observed is the overload on the institutions and the inability to deal with prospective patients. Majority of the beneficiaries seek to get treated at the private hospitals given the quality, service and fear of transmission. To overcome such challenges in the implementation, the greater authority shall be given to states to make the ground level institutions accountable. An enhanced engagement shall be made with the stakeholders to overcome the loopholes that occur at the ground level. A separate body shall be established for the assessment of the scheme in the private sector and make the engaged hospitals accountable. Efforts must be made to improve rural infrastructure.

Acknowledgements

This research article has been written as part of the summer internship project (from July, 2020 to August, 2020) under the supervision of Dr. Mukesh Kumar Mishra, Secretary General, Krityanand UNESCO Club, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand, India.

References

- Dong, D., Naib, P., Smith O., Chhabra Sheena. (2019). Raising the Bar: Analysing of PM-JAY High-value claims. *National Health Authority*.
<https://pmjay.gov.in/research-report>
- Gopichandran, V., Subramaniam, S. (2020). Response to COVID-19: An ethical imperative to build a resilient health system in India. *Indian Journal of Medical Ethics*. 5(2)\
DOI: 10.20529/IJME.2020.026
- Hooda, K., (2020). Decoding Ayushman Bharat: A Policy Economy Perspective. *Economic and Political Weekly*. 55 (25)
<https://www.epw.in/journal/2020/25/special-articles/decoding-ayushman-bharat.html>
- Lahariya, C. (2018). Ayushman Bharat Program and Universal Health Coverage In India. *Indian Pediatrics*. 55.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13312-018-1341-1>
- Malhi, R., Goel, D., Gambheer, R., Brar P., Behal, D., Bhardwaj, A. (2020). Rashtriya Swasthya Bima Yojana. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*. 9(2).
[10.4103/jfmprc.jfmprc_959_19](https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmprc.jfmprc_959_19)
- Mundra, D. (2018). Ayushman Bharat- India's National Health Protection Scheme. *Healthmanagement*. 3(18).
<https://healthmanagement.org/c/hospital/issuearticle/ayushman-bharat-india-s-national-health-protection-mission>
- Pawar, Manohar. (2012). The adoption of Rights-based approach to welfarism in India. *Journal of Comparative Social Welfare*. 28(1).
[10.1080/17486831.2012.636253](https://doi.org/10.1080/17486831.2012.636253)
- PTI. (2020, May 22). Around 2,300 patients availed free COVID-19 treatment in hospitals under Ayushman Bharat: Official. *Economic Times*
<https://health.economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/policy/around-2300-patients-availed-free-covid-treatment-in-hospitals-under-ayushman-bharat-official/75881709>
- Smith, O., Naib, P., Sehgal, P., Chhabra, S. (2020). PM-JAY under Lockdown: Evidence on utilisation Trends. *National Health Authority*.
https://pmjay.gov.in/sites/default/files/2020-06/Policy-Brief-8_PM-JAY-under-Lockdown-Evidence_12-06-20_NHA_WB.pdf
- Srivastava, R. (2008). Towards universal protection in India in a Rights-based Paradigm. *Indian Journal of Human Development*. 2(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0973703020080106>